

Modelling surface and underground streams in drainage network computation

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Abstract

Drainage networks can be computed from high-resolution digital elevation models derived from airborne lidar point clouds. However, before mapping the streams, drainage enforcement must be applied to alter the model and remove local depressions that can interrupt the computed flow. This includes carving the terrain at culvert locations to direct flows under roads embankment. This operation remains approximate and leads to more alterations of the terrain. This work is part of a project that aims to integrate culverts into the calculation of the drainage network. This would allow for the inclusion of underground components, without altering the DEM or requiring manual intervention. The paper presents a new conceptual model that describes the drainage network, including both surface and underground streams, and drainage basins with their divides and provides a richer description of the drainage. Preliminary results are also presented in a case study.

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1 Introduction

The acquisition of highly detailed geospatial data through lidar technology has facilitated the production of drainage networks from very high-resolution digital elevation models (DEMs) over large areas. The D8 method [8] is still commonly used to produce drainage maps. But, on these DEMs, roads become visible with their embankments, and modeled drainage flows are detoured along the roads. In reality, streams cross road embankments through underground culverts which are not visible on the DEM.

To overcome this issue, the DEM is altered at places along the roads. Two approaches are considered [6]. If culvert positions are known, the DEM is burnt, i.e. is lowered, at these locations; otherwise, breaching techniques are used, i.e. the DEM is carved to connect local minimums in depressions to lower points in the vicinity and avoid flow interruption [7]. [6] compared several methods and showed the importance of having a complete database of real culverts in order to obtain the most representative stream network from the DEM-derived drainage modeling. However, because of the inaccuracy in the computations, the DEM has to be burnt on a significant length longer than the reality to ensure that the modelled flow will be diverted accordingly to the culvert pathway. Such an approach alters the DEM and can lead to inconsistencies between the original terrain and the drainage. Furthermore,

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the resulting drainage network is described as a network of lines without further semantic information about the streams (on surface or underground) and the type of connections.

Recently, a new approach, the *Extended Surface Network* (ESN), was proposed. It is based on the computation of a network of thalwegs and ridges from which it extracts a stream network [5]. The structure does not alter the DEM and can also compute drainage basins. Furthermore, it guarantees the topological consistency between all elements of the network. However, like the D8 method, it does not handle culverts. Therefore, it is essential to develop an approach that directly integrates culverts into the linear network, enabling precise, automatic calculation of the drainage network, including surface and underground flows, and guarantees flow consistency with the original DEM. The objective of our research project is thus to propose a new model that integrates culverts in its definition and an algorithm that takes them into account in the computation of flow direction and accumulation.

Ontology design patterns (ODP) have already been proposed for the description of terrain features or water features [3]. However, they were developed as separate pieces of ontologies and do not integrate all features of interest for the modelling of a drainage network. As a first step towards the integration of culverts in drainage computation, this paper presents a new conceptual model that describes the drainage network, including culverts as underground elements. The design of such a model facilitates the representation and implementation of a data structure that encapsulates the intricacies of both surface and subsurface hydrological networks in a manner that is both comprehensive and adaptable.

This article first presents an overview of existing ODPs and the ESN. In section 3, we propose a conceptual model that formalises the representation of the drainage network including flow lines and other salient elements of the terrain. We then present preliminary results obtained on an implementation of our model. The final section concludes and presents directions for future works.

2 Literature review

2.1 Surface and water network ontologies

A surface network (SN) is a Morse-Smale Complex computed from a DEM [4]. As such, it provides a network of critical points and lines forming a skeleton of the terrain (Figure 1). The SN provides a partition of the terrain into *descending cells* (or *hills*, in red in Figure 1) and a partition into *ascending cells* (or *dales*, in blue in Figure 1). The intersection of an ascending and a descending cell is a *Morse-Smale cell* or *hillslope* (in yellow in Figure 1). Sinha et al. [9] proposed a Surface Network Ontology Design Pattern (SNODP). It formalises the different elements of the SN together with their topological relationships.

The SNODP includes abstract classes for elements (or cells in the Morse-Smale theory) of different dimensions. *Peak*, *Pit* and *Saddle* are all types of *CriticalPoint*. *Ridge* and *Thalweg* (or *CourseLine*) are *SlopeLine*. *Hill* and *Dale* are two kinds of *District* (cells of dimension 2). In the SNODP, hillslopes are named *Territory*. *SlopeLines* establish connections between critical points. All these elements carry their own semantics and are parts of the *SurfaceNetwork* class. This class facilitates the organization of parts within a specific SN, enabling the differentiation of unique surface components.

Other elements that are not defined in the SN but represent relevant terrain elements are also included in the SNODP. They are *Basin* and *Hilltop* that define the area within a dale that is below its lowest saddle and the area within a hill that is above the highest saddle. While not crucial, basin and hilltop classes offer supplementary insights into surface morphology. Finally, *Contour* describes contour lines that run perpendicular to ridges and

■ **Figure 1** Surface network (modified from [5]). The yellow hillslope is the intersection of the blue dale and the red hill.

thalwegs. Each class is defined with specific axioms capturing its semantics and relationships with other classes within the pattern.

Despite its comprehensive structure, the SNODP only focuses on the topography and does not include the drainage network. In [3], authors present a Surface Water Feature Ontology Design Pattern (SWFODP). It is divided in two modules. The dry module describes concave terrain features that can contain water and the wet module captures the semantics of hydrological features. Wet features are all contained by dry features. Features also form a network since areal and linear elements are connected by junction nodes.

Although the authors showed that the SNODP and the SWFODP shared common elements, both ODP were not integrated together. Thalwegs in the SN do not necessarily correspond to streams, since there is no indication whether water flows through them. The node classification is different. In the SWFODP, nodes initiate or terminate flows or connect streams together. The SN records nodes that have a topographical importance (pits, saddles and peaks). However, although the SN relies on mathematical foundations, the robust computation of the SN was still an open problem [2]. Thus, authors in [3] consider that the SN describes abstract features that do not correspond to real world features.

Furthermore, neither the SNODP nor the SWFODP include the semantics to describe drainage basins while these are important elements in the definition of a drainage network. The SWFODP only considers water features and their containers. In the SN, ridges are only a subset of the drainage divides delineating drainage basins [1] and thalwegs miss a flow direction. Thus, the stream ordering and accumulation that are required to compute a drainage network from a DEM cannot be expressed within the SN.

2.2 The Extended Surface Network

Recently, a new data structure, the extended surface network (ESN), was presented in [5] to alleviate limitations presented in [1, 2]. The ESN (Figure 2) extends the definition of the SN by (1) adding more ridges that represent drainage divides and (2) adding a flow direction to each thalweg.

In the ESN, ridges (red lines in Figure 2) are initiated not only at saddle points but at each node where thalwegs start or arrive. This allows for the definition for each thalweg of a dale delineated by ridges that contains all the flows converging towards this thalweg. Thus, the flow on each side of a ridge converges towards a different thalweg and ridges of the ESN

■ **Figure 2** Extended surface network (modified from [5]). Grey surfaces are dales.

correspond to drainage divides.

The set of thalwegs is not modified and still forms the same hill partition of the terrain as in the SN. Since more ridges were added, dales (grey surfaces in Figure 2) form a more detailed partition than the one in the SN. Dales are still delineated by ridges. However, they are no longer centred on pits but on thalwegs (blue lines in Figure 2).

The flow direction is computed to guarantee that it is not interrupted by spurious pits. Therefore, the concept of puddle is introduced. A *Puddle* is a depression characterised by an outlet and represents the part of the terrain below the outlet. While in the SNODP, a basin is inside a dale, in the ESN, a puddle can cover several dales. While the flow along a thalweg is normally directed towards the lower end, inside a puddle, it is directed towards the outlet.

Once the flow has been directed, the drainage basin of a thalweg can be defined by the set of all dales located upstream. Authors in [5] show that the ESN can be used to compute the flow accumulation and the drainage basin of each thalweg without drainage enforcement and thus without altering the DEM. Streams are initiated according to an accumulation threshold and the stream network is composed of all thalwegs whose accumulation is greater than the threshold.

As mentioned earlier, the ESN presents an alternative to the traditional D8 method to compute a drainage network. Because it relies on a topological structure recording different types of lines and nodes, it provides a richer semantic than the network computed from D8. However, it can only record streams on the surface and the model needs to be extended to integrate underground streams and provide a new algorithm to connect culverts with the drainage on the surface.

3 The drainage network model

We present in this section a new conceptual model to represent drainage networks. The objective is not only to be able to formalise the semantics properties but also to have a model that can be implemented for the mapping of the drainage system. It shall include both surface and subsurface streams but also other relevant elements such as drainage basins.

The conceptual model relies on the structure presented in the ESN. This way, the model can integrate both topographic and hydrographic features. A further difference with the SWFODP presented above is that it does not distinguish wet and dry features. Indeed, with the need to map not only permanent streams but also temporary or ephemeral streams, all watercourses through which water can flow shall be mapped. Since thalwegs are lines of flow convergence, we consider that thalwegs can all be watercourses.

All critical nodes and lines of the ESN are also found in the drainage network so that the drainage network provides the same terrain partitions as the ESN. Thus, these nodes are

■ **Figure 3** Drainage Network Conceptual Model.

feature nodes in the drainage (*CriticalPoint* in Figure 3). Because the ESN assigns a flow direction to each thalweg, nodes can also be classified based on stream connections (*Fluence* in Figure 3). If two or more streams merge into one, the node is a confluence node. If the flow is divided into several streams, the node is a diffluence. A node where one stream arrives and one stream leaves is a transfluence.

Both *CriticalPoint* and *Fluence* classes overlap but the subclasses of each class are disjoint. For example, a saddle connecting two thalwegs can be a transfluence if the flow passes through or a spring if it does not receive any flow. A node that receives flow but from where no flow leaves is a sink. Because the flow is not stopped in local depressions, most pits are not sinks but transfluences.

Critical lines are thalwegs and drainage divides. Ridges of the SN are seen as a subset of drainage divides. They are the lines starting from a saddle while other drainage divides are initiated from pits and thalweg junctions. Thalwegs do not connect to ridge junctions and peaks. They have at least two attributes: a flow accumulation and a flow direction.

The *Surface* class includes both hills and dales. Hills align with the description of descending cells (2-cells of the Morse-Smale complex). Each hill therefore contains exactly one peak. Dales in the ESN are built around thalwegs and thus each dale contains exactly one thalweg. The boundary of hills and dales is defined by rings of thalwegs and divides. As shown in [5], a surface can have holes and contain dangling lines that do not belong to a ring. Topological relationships between lines and surfaces are also shown in Figure 3.

Since ridges of the SN are contained in the ESN, depressions from the SN are also defined in the ESN and are formed by an aggregation of dales. Their boundary is a ring of ridges. Each depression is associated to a single pit. Dales located upstream a thalweg can also be

retrieved so that drainage basins can be defined for any stream. A drainage basin (Basin in Figure 3) is delineated by a ring of divides.

These elements represent the part of the drainage above the ground. Culverts are added and connected to these elements to model the part below ground. While thalwegs are natural watercourses, culverts are artificial watercourses. As such, culverts are also defined as watercourses and are connected to other watercourses by fluences. A culvert also has a flow direction from which its entrance and exit can be inferred. Since the flow that enters a culvert is rerouted from existing thalwegs, the entry node of a culvert is either an existing node or a thalweg junction that is added to the network. The exit of the culvert is also connected to a thalweg. That means that if no thalweg is found, a new thalweg is initiated at the exit of the culvert, forming a transfluence. This operation also requires the introduction of divides to maintain the consistency of the ridge and thalweg network. Since the culvert is underground, it is not associated to any dale. The drainage basin of a culvert is then defined as the union of basins of the thalwegs that flow into the culvert.

Whether water runs in a watercourse is defined by the flow accumulation. Several accumulation thresholds can be given and associated to different flow regimes [6]. Thus different types of watercourses are defined according to the flow (permanent, intermittent, ephemeral or dry). Since culverts are also watercourses, they are also characterised by a flow regime. Accumulation thresholds can be set by the user depending on terrain-related parameters such as the type of soil or the slope.

4 Results

The model was implemented for the calculation of a drainage network. It is based on the algorithm defined in [5]. Input data for the computation are a DEM and a database of culverts. Each culvert is defined by a line segment and can contain other attributes such as its diameter or the material (orange line in Figure 4). A first step of the computation consists in connecting culverts with thalwegs. With a raster DEM, culvert lines are discretised (cyan line in Figure 4). Usually, the extremities of the culvert already intersect thalwegs running in the ditches alongside the roads. However, in some cases, it was necessary to initiate a new thalweg at the end of the culvert to connect with the network.

The algorithm was applied to a one-metre resolution DEM of the Ruisseau des Eaux Volées basin (BEREV) and a culvert database. The DEM was provided by the Ministère des Ressources Naturelles et des Forêts of Québec province, Canada. Culverts were located by photo-interpretation and during a field trip. Results shown in the figure 4 correspond to those presented in the conceptual model. Two classes of nodes are present, CriticalPoint representing the ESN and Flueuce corresponding to the drainage network. The streams model both surface and subsurface flow (Thalwegs with water and Culverts) and are defined according to an accumulation threshold.

5 Conclusion and future works

Traditionally, the drainage network is computed by flow accumulation techniques from raster DEMs. The method yields a linear network that contains limited semantics and topology. In this paper, we present a new conceptual model that includes drainage basins and drainage divides as well as underground elements that are not visible on the DEM. The model adds the concept of culvert and describes the connections with other elements of the drainage. It preserves also all the knowledge expressed by the SN, which allows for the modelling of

■ **Figure 4** Thalwegs, culvert and nodes of a drainage network.

drainage basins and maintains the topological consistency with the DEM.

The model was implemented and preliminary results are presented on a case study. The model provides a richer semantics and was able to compute a correct flow direction and a valid drainage network. The computation was also done without altering the DEM, ensuring the consistency between the terrain and the drainage.

Next step is the analysis and validation of the results, with a comparison with networks computed with traditional methods and with field data. While puddles can be associated with water bodies, they are not integrated in the stream network which remains a linear network. A direction for future works is the integration of areal features as proper hydrographic features such as lakes or wetlands, extending further the conceptual model.

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